

Appendix A. Crosswalk of DigComp 3.0 competences and CSTA Standards Draft 3.0

DigiComp3.0		CSTA Standards Draft 3.0	
Competence area and descriptor	Competence and descriptor	Concept/Pillar/Disposition	Subconcept+overview
1 Information search, evaluation and management	1.1 Browsing, searching and filtering information	3 Data & Analysis 4 Systems & Security 5 Computing & Society D: Curiosity	3.1 Data Fundamentals 4.1 Hardware and Software 5.2 Emerging Technologies
To articulate information needs, and to search for, locate and retrieve digital information and content. To judge the relevance of the source and its content in digital environments. To critically evaluate digital sources, content, and processes used to generate them. To store, manage, organise and analyse digital information and data.	To articulate information needs, to know how and where to search for information and content in digital environments, and to access and navigate between them. To select appropriate digital tools to create, implement and update searches in digital environments and to be able to distinguish between relevant and irrelevant information and content.		3.1 Data is ... collected by people 4.1 Computing systems use hardware and software to communicate and process information in digital form. 5.2 In early grades, students learn how computing technology aids their daily life. They evaluate choices and consequences related to emerging technologies and identify problems that these advances could address. In middle grades, students evaluate how emerging technologies impact user experiences, while attending to ethical design principles. D: Asking questions and exploring beyond assigned work.
	1.2 Evaluating information	4 Systems & Security P: Ethics & Social Responsibility D: Critical Thinking	4.4 Impacts of Computing Systems P: Use computing for positive social impact. D: Using reasoning and evidence to analyze and refine solutions.
	To assess and compare the credibility and reliability of sources of information and content in digital environments. To interpret and critically evaluate information and content in digital environments, and the processes used to generate them.		4.4 While there have been benefits, there have also been harms and the creation of new problems. P: Evaluate whether potential benefits of computing solutions outweigh possible harms.
	1.3 Managing information	3 Data & Analysis P: Computational Thinking	3.1 Data Fundamentals 3.2 Data Processing 3.3 Data Investigation 3.4 Impacts of Data Science P: Develop and use abstractions

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	To organise, store and retrieve information and data in digital environments. To collect, process and analyse information and data in structured digital environments.		<p>3.1 Data is generated and collected by people, often using computing technologies such as sensors and other automated systems. In early grades, students learn about different types of data and how data is generated, collected, and organized.</p> <p>3.2 Computing devices process data to make it useful for analysis. In earlier grades, students learn how to use computational tools to manipulate data: filtering, grouping, summarizing, transforming, and reshaping data. As students progress, they apply computational methods to: automate data cleaning, identify and handle errors in data, and prepare data for analysis.</p> <p>3.3 Data investigations are a multistep process. When conducting data investigations, students pose data questions, use computational tools to collect and analyze data, create data visualizations, generate insights, and tell the story of their data. In early grades, students focus on asking simple questions that can be answered with small datasets.</p> <p>3.4 Students explore how data influences decision-making and impacts individuals and communities. P: a. Extract common features and patterns from data,</p>
2 Communication and collaboration	2.1 Interacting through and with digital technologies	4 Systems & Security 5 Computing & Society	4.1 Hardware and Software 4.2 Security 4.4 Impacts of Computing Systems 5.1 History of Computing 5.3 Humans and Computing

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To interact, share, communicate and collaborate in digital environments while being aware of cultural, generational and other diversity and the features and limitations of digital technologies. To participate in society through digital technologies. To assert one's rights and exercise choice in digital environments. To manage one's digital presence, identity and reputation.	To interact through and with a variety of digital technologies, and to use appropriate digital communication for a given context.		<p>4.1 In early grades, students learn how systems use both hardware and software to represent and process information. As they progress, students gain a deeper understanding of the interactions between hardware and software at multiple levels within computing systems.</p> <p>4.2 As they progress, students learn about information transmission across devices, network design, and how to protect networks from different types of threats.</p> <p>4.4 Humans created computing systems to accomplish tasks and solve problems. ... In early grades, students examine the impacts of computing systems on individuals. As they progress, students learn about the impacts of computing systems on global society.</p> <p>5.1 In early grades, students first identify how computing is used in daily life.</p> <p>5.3 Humans and computing technologies are intricately connected. They will investigate how humans leverage computing to solve problems and examine the motivations behind designing and building these systems.</p>
	2.2 Sharing through digital technologies	3 Data & Analysis P: Inclusive Collaboration	3.4 Impacts of Data Science P: Act responsibly in computing collaborations
	To share information and content ethically and responsibly with others through appropriate digital technologies.		3.4 Students examine the benefits, risks, and ethical considerations around data use. P: b. Participate reliably in computing teamwork, share responsibility for project outcomes, and meet development deadlines. P: c. Reflect on contributions to computing projects, including technical decisions and team interactions, to improve technical and collaboration skills.
2.3 Engaging in citizenship through digital technologies	1 Algorithms & Design 5 Computing & Society P: Ethics & Social Responsibility	1.4 Impacts of Algorithms and Design 5.1 History of Computing 5.2 Emerging Technologies P: Use computing for positive social impact.	

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	To participate in society through the ethical and responsible use of digital platforms and services. To seek opportunities for self-empowerment and participation through appropriate digital technologies. To be aware of and assert one's rights, and to exercise choice, in digital environments.		<p>1.4 Algorithms can have positive and negative effects on people and society. It is important to evaluate not only how well an algorithm works, but also who it benefits, who it may unintentionally harm, and why.</p> <p>5.1 Students also explore the societal impacts of computing innovations.</p> <p>P: a. Imagine and create computing technologies that solve problems, strengthen communities, and improve quality of life.</p> <p>5.2. They explain how emerging technologies can inspire innovation and help people accomplish tasks in new ways. In later grades, students understand the core computational principles behind emerging technologies and compare the ethical considerations of emerging technologies, using various frameworks.</p> <p>P: b. Evaluate whether potential benefits of computing solutions outweigh possible harms. Ensure that harms are not concentrated on specific groups and avoid serious environmental harm.</p> <p>P: c. Explain design trade-offs in computing projects, including what values these decisions reflect and what was prioritized or sacrificed.</p>
	2.4 Collaborating through digital technologies	P: Inclusive Collaboration	P: Act responsibly in computing collaborations
	To use digital technologies ethically and responsibly for collaborative purposes, and for the co-construction and co-creation of information, resources and knowledge.		<p>P: a. Cultivate working relationships with individuals possessing diverse perspectives, skills, and personalities.</p> <p>P: b. Participate reliably in computing teamwork, share responsibility for project outcomes, and meet development deadlines.</p>
	2.5 Digital behaviour	<p>1 Algorithms & Design</p> <p>4 Systems & Security</p> <p>P: Inclusive Collaboration</p> <p>P: Ethics & Social Responsibility</p> <p>P: Human-Centered Design</p>	<p>1.4 Impacts of Algorithms and Design</p> <p>4.2 Security</p> <p>4.4 Impacts of Computing Systems</p> <p>P: Communicate effectively about computing</p> <p>P: Respect others' rights when creating computational technologies.</p> <p>P: Understand and involve diverse users in design decisions</p>

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	To be aware of behavioural norms, and to know how to behave respectfully while using digital technologies and interacting in digital environments. To adapt communication to specific contexts, and to be aware of and respect cultural, generational and other diversity in digital environments.		<p>1.4 As students progress, they learn to identify possible consequences of algorithmic decisions and they apply human-centered design principles to develop and refine computational algorithms. In later grades, students critically analyze the societal impacts of algorithms, including issues of fairness, equity, accessibility, and bias, and consider how algorithmic systems can shape real-world experiences.</p> <p>4.2 Transmitting information securely across networks requires appropriate protection. In early grades, students learn how to protect their personal information.</p> <p>4.4 In early grades, students examine the impacts of computing systems on individuals. As they progress, students learn about the impacts of computing systems on global society.</p> <p>P: a. Share technical ideas and explain computing concepts clearly to different audiences. b. Give and actively listen to others' input and constructive feedback. Consider diverse perspectives and multiple solutions to technical challenges.</p> <p>P: b. Respect users' privacy and protect their data. Give users choices about how their information is collected and used. Only collect the minimum amount of information necessary.</p> <p>P: a. Learn about different people's experiences with computing technologies, including those with different abilities, backgrounds, and needs. b. Gather input and feedback from diverse users throughout the design and development process to help create positive user experiences.</p>
	2.6 Managing digital identity To manage one or multiple digital identities. To take actions to help protect one's digital reputation (how one is perceived based on online presence), and to manage one's digital footprint (the data that is produced through use of and by digital platforms and services).	3 Data & Analysis	3.4 Impacts of Data Science 3.4 As students progress, they explore issues related to bias in data, data privacy, artificial intelligence and machine learning, and large-scale societal and environmental impacts of data science applications.
3 Content creation	3.1 Developing digital content To use digital technologies ethically and responsibly to create and edit a variety of content. To express oneself through digital means.	D: Creativity	D: Generating original, meaningful computing ideas and projects.
To create and edit digital content. To improve and integrate information and content into an existing body of knowledge while understanding how copyright and licences are	3.2 Integrating and re-elaborating digital content	2 Programming 3 Data & Analysis	2.2 Program Development 3.3 Data Investigation 3.4 Impacts of Data Science

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to be applied, adopting an ethical and responsible approach in the creation, improvement and integration of digital content. To know how to apply computational thinking and programming techniques to give instructions to a computer system.	To modify, refine and integrate new information and content into existing knowledge and resources to create new and original content and knowledge.		2.2 As students progress, they focus more on building on existing code, modularizing code, documenting code, and using AI tools to support their programming. 3.3 As students progress, they work with larger datasets, asking and answering more sophisticated questions that consider variability and relationships between multiple variables. 3.4 Students explore how data influences decision-making and impacts individuals and communities. ... In early grades, students discuss how using data can help them make more informed decisions in their daily lives.
	3.3 Copyright and licences	P: Ethics & Social Responsibility	P: Respect others' rights when creating computational technologies.
	To understand how copyright and licences, as well as associated legal and ethical issues, apply to digital content, and how to correctly apply them.		P: Respect other creators of computational technologies. Only use others' work with permission and give appropriate attribution.
	3.4 Computational thinking and programming	1 Algorithms & Design 2 Programming P: Computational Thinking	1.1 Algorithm Fundamentals P: Define computational problems 1.2 Problem Solving 2.1 Programming Fundamentals
	To understand and implement steps to analyse a problem, recognise sub-problems, and plan and develop a sequence of instructions for a computing system to solve a given problem or to perform a specific task.		1.1 Designing algorithms, or step-by-step solutions to a task, are an essential component of CS. In early grades, students identify and create algorithms reflecting tasks in their daily lives. As students progress, they develop more complex algorithms and create visual representations of their solutions. P: a. Identify real-world problems that can be solved computationally using rule-based approaches, data-driven approaches (e.g., machine learning), or hybrid methods. 1.2 While there may be many approaches to addressing a task, optimizing an algorithm can result in more efficient and accurate solutions. As students progress, they begin to evaluate the efficiency and accuracy of computational algorithms running under different conditions and use problem-solving skills to explore algorithms' underlying opaque systems. 2.1 Across grade levels, students focus on reading and interpreting code, translating algorithms into code, and understanding programming languages' types, syntax, and semantics. Although programming constructs repeat across this subconcept, their complexity is expected to increase as students advance through grade levels. P: a. Generate and evaluate multiple solution approaches to determine which best meet the defined criteria given the constraints. b. Plan the development of computational solutions. c. Implement solutions by developing or modifying artifacts through traditional programming, model training, or hybrid

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<p>4 Safety, wellbeing and responsible use</p> <p>To protect devices, content, personal data and privacy in digital environments. To support physical, mental and social wellbeing of oneself and others, and to be aware of the benefits and risks of digital technologies for wellbeing and social inclusion. To be aware of the environmental impact of digital technologies and their use, to take action to reduce such impact, and to use digital technologies to support sustainability.</p>	<p>4.1 Protecting devices</p> <p>To apply safety and cybersecurity measures in order to protect digital devices and content. To be aware of the evolving nature of risks and threats in digital environments, and to have due regard to security of digital devices and their contents.</p>	4 Systems & Security	<p>4.1 Hardware and Software</p> <p>4.2 Security</p> <p>4.1 Computing systems use hardware and software to communicate and process information in digital form.</p> <p>4.2 Transmitting information securely across networks requires appropriate protection. As they progress, students learn about information transmission across devices, network design, and how to protect networks from different types of threats.</p>
	<p>4.2 Protecting personal data and privacy</p> <p>To be aware of and exercise one's rights in relation to personal data and privacy in digital environments. To evaluate and manage privacy risks and protect personal data and privacy in digital environments. To use and share one's own and others' personal data safely, ethically and responsibly.</p>	4 Systems & Security	<p>4.2 Security</p> <p>4.2 Transmitting information securely across networks requires appropriate protection. In early grades, students learn how to protect their personal information.</p>
	<p>4.3 Supporting wellbeing</p> <p>To use digital technologies in ways that support wellbeing and inclusion. To minimise risks and threats to physical, mental and social wellbeing of oneself and others while using digital technologies. To balance usage of digital technologies with offline activities to support wellbeing. To take action to help protect oneself and others from possible dangers in digital environments (e.g. cyberbullying, harmful content), and know how to respond to such dangers.</p>	5 Computing & Society D: Sense of Belonging	<p>5.3 Humans and Computing</p> <p>5.3 Humans and computing technologies are intricately connected. Students will learn that people are the fundamental creators of these technologies and will differentiate between tasks best suited for humans versus those for computing. They will investigate how humans leverage computing to solve problems and examine the motivations behind designing and building these systems. A critical focus is distinguishing between human and computational learning processes, enabling students to decide when and where computing technologies, including AI, are appropriate and helpful. As they progress, students will analyze the trade-offs of using AI-powered solutions and evaluate how human choices in designing, deploying, and regulating AI influence its risks, benefits, and long-term societal impacts.</p> <p>D: Feeling included, respected, and recognized in the CS community.</p>
	<p>4.4 Environmental impacts of digital technologies</p>	3 Data & Analysis P: Ethics & Social Responsibility	<p>3.4 Impacts of Data Science</p> <p>P: Use computing for positive social impact.</p>

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	To be aware of the environmental impacts of digital technologies, including device production, operation, repair, recycling, disposal, data storage infrastructure, energy consumption and usage of tools and applications. To take action to reduce such impact and to use digital technologies to support sustainability.		3.4 As students progress, they explore issues related to ... and environmental impacts of data science applications. P: b. Evaluate whether potential benefits of computing solutions outweigh possible harms. Ensure that harms are not concentrated on specific groups and avoid serious environmental harm.
5 Problem identification and solving	5.1 Identifying and solving technical problems	D: Resourcefulness	
To identify and assess needs, and to use digital technologies adapt digital environments to meet them. To identify and resolve technical and conceptual problems and problem situations in digital environments. To use digital technologies to make improvements in or new solutions for processes and products. To build capabilities to operate autonomously in digital environments. To stay informed about digital technological developments and their implications.	To identify technical problems when operating digital devices and in digital environments, and to solve them through a variety of means.		D: Strategically seeking tools, people, and references to solve problems.
	5.2 Identifying needs and digital technological responses	2 Programming 5 Computing & Society D: Resourcefulness	2.2 Program Development 5.2 Emerging Technologies
	To assess one's own and others' needs and to evaluate, select, use and adapt digital technologies to meet them. To adjust and customise digital environments to the needs (e.g. accessibility), contexts and goals of oneself and others.		2.2 Programming involves paying attention to the organization and structure of code. In early grades, students strengthen their understanding of how to create programs. As students progress, they focus more on building on existing code, modularizing code, documenting code, and using AI tools to support their programming. 5.2 Computing is a rapidly developing discipline. While other concepts cover what students should know about the current field of CS, this subconcept focuses on recently developed technologies that have the potential to significantly impact society. D: Strategically seeking tools, people, and references to solve problems.
	5.3 Identifying creative solutions using digital technologies	P: Computational Thinking	P: Create computational artifacts
	To use digital technologies to make improvements in or new solutions for processes and products, using a human-centric approach. To engage individually and collectively in critical thinking processes, and the creative and purposeful use of digital technologies, to understand and resolve conceptual problems and problem situations.		P: a. Generate and evaluate multiple solution approaches to determine which best meet the defined criteria given the constraints. b. Plan the development of computational solutions. c. Implement solutions by developing or modifying artifacts through traditional programming, model training, or hybrid methods.
	5.4 Identifying and addressing digital competence needs	D: Persistence	

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	To recognise where one’s own digital competence needs to be improved or updated. To address digital competence needs within a broader process of lifelong learning, building capacity and autonomy. To support others with their digital competence development. To stay informed about digital technological developments and their personal, professional and societal implications.		D: Connecting past experiences to future learning choices
Out-of-scope concepts for DigComp 3.0		1 Algorithms & Design	1.3 Machine Learning Machine learning is a subfield of artificial intelligence in which computers “learn” from data in order to make decisions without being explicitly programmed to do so. This subconcept includes content that is key for understanding foundational components of artificial intelligence. In early grades, students recognize patterns used by people and machines for decision-making. As they advance, students explore how AI models evolve with new training data, train AI models for classification or prediction, and analyze the relationship between training data properties and AI model output. By high school, students justify the selection of AI algorithms, evaluate training data for quality and bias, and develop AI models for specific tasks using appropriate data and tools.
		2 Programming	2.3 Reading and Documenting Code In a world where AI assistants can generate code based on a prompt, the ability to read and interpret code is increasingly important. In early grades, students describe how code completes tasks including explaining code functionality, program development steps, and how specific code segments contribute to a program’s purpose. They also learn to document programs for clarity and create embedded or external documentation for projects. Later on, students evaluate AI-generated code for accuracy, reliability, and usability.

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		2 Programming	2.4 Testing and Refining Code Ensuring that code works as intended is key to building reliable programs. In early grades, students focus on identifying and fixing errors in their programs. As students progress, they focus on more complex troubleshooting strategies, optimizing their code for efficiency and usability and assessing the accuracy and bias of AI-generated code.
		2 Programming	2.5 Data Handling Understanding how programs structure and store data is necessary for successful programming. In early grades, students focus on identifying and labeling data in their daily lives and in age-appropriate programming languages. As students progress, they learn about and manipulate more complex data types.
		3 Data & Analysis	3.1 Data Fundamentals Metadata is “data about data.” Metadata provides context about data, including its origin, structure, and purpose. As they progress, students gain experience with larger and more varied datasets, learn about more advanced data types and organization structures, and develop data documentation.
		4 Systems & Security	4.3 Networks Computing devices communicate with one another across networks to share information. In early grades, students learn that computers connect them to other people, places, and things around the world. As they progress, students gain a deeper understanding of how information is sent and received across different types of networks.

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		5 Computing & Society	<p>5.1 History of Computing The history of computing reflects contributions from many societies and knowledge traditions. ... Then they focus on how technologies have evolved over time in response to social, scientific, and economic needs. In middle grades, students evaluate how historical challenges led to computing innovations and compare the roles played by individuals, communities, organizations, and governments in advancing these technologies. ... In later grades, students delve into the main eras of computing history and understand policy and legislation related to computing technologies. They also analyze the historic impacts of technologies, giving consideration to the factors that contributed to disparities across communities.</p>
			<p>5.4 Career Exploration Computing is foundational to nearly every career field. Understanding the role of computing in the workplace prepares students to make informed choices about their futures. In early grades, students recognize how digital tools and technologies support everyday work across professions. In middle grades, students explore how computational thinking drives innovation across industries and examine the ethical challenges that professionals may encounter. In later grades, students connect computing to their personal interests and career goals, investigate computing-related pathways, and analyze how advancements in technology foster new opportunities for growth across diverse fields.</p>
		P: Inclusive Collaboration	<p>P: Manage computing projects a. Establish shared goals, break the work into discrete tasks, and set development milestones. b. Document code and development processes.</p>
		P: Computational Thinking	<p>P: Define computational problems b. Clearly state criteria for success and identify constraints. c. Decompose complex problems into manageable subproblems.</p>

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			<p>P: Develop and use abstractions</p> <p>b. Create reusable modules and procedures that can apply to multiple situations to reduce complexity.</p> <p>c. Model phenomena and develop simulations, using rule-based and data-driven approaches, to understand and evaluate potential outcomes.</p>
			<p>P: Test and refine computational artifacts</p> <p>a. Test, debug, and troubleshoot computational artifacts systematically using appropriate methods, such as generating test cases for rule-based programs and accuracy evaluation for machine learning models.</p> <p>b. Iteratively refine and optimize solutions to meet criteria for success.</p>
		P: Human-Centered Design	<p>P: Use iterative design processes</p> <p>a. Start with simple prototypes and continuously test and refine solutions to ensure usability and accessibility.</p>
			<p>P: Design computational technologies that empower and inform users</p> <p>a. Respect users' autonomy. Be transparent about how computational technologies make decisions that affect users. Give users control over how they interact with technologies rather than leveraging human limitations to serve creators' interests over users' interests.</p> <p>b. Consider the benefits and harms of human-like behaviors in computational technologies (e.g., conversational AI) and how they influence user perceptions and actions.</p>